

“A Study To Assess The Effectiveness Of Structured Teaching Programme On Programme On Knowledge Regarding Selected Behavioural Problems Of Pre-School Children’s Parents At Selected Pre-School At Dewas M.P.”

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DOI [10.5281/zenodo.14620157](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14620157)

ABSTRACT

Behavioral problems among preschool children are a growing concern, impacting their mental health, development, and overall well-being. This study evaluates the effectiveness of a structured teaching program on the knowledge of parents regarding selected behavioral problems in preschool children at Dewas, M.P. A pre-test post-test design was adopted, with 60 mothers as participants. Findings revealed significant improvement in parental knowledge after the intervention, with a t-value of 18.525. Demographic variables such as age, education, and occupation showed a significant association with pre-test scores. The study underscores the importance of educational programs in enhancing awareness and promoting early intervention.

Keywords: Behavioral problems, STP, preschool children

INTRODUCTION

Today’s children are tomorrow’s responsible citizens of the world. There is a great emphasis on children these days because of the recognition that a very substantial proportion of the world’s population, 35-45% constitute young children. The future of our country depends on positive mental health of our young people. However, nearly one in five children and adolescents have emotional and behavioural disorders at some point of time in their young lives, regardless of their geographic region or socio-economic status.

Recent evidence by WHO indicates that by 2020 childhood neuropsychiatric disorders will rise proportionately by over 50%, and would be the fifth most common cause of morbidity, mortality and disability among children. Epidemiologically estimates suggest that approximately 14-20% of all children from birth

to 18 years of age have some type of psychiatric disorders and about 3% to 5% have serious disorders.

As per Child International Organization, 2016

Around one in ten children under the age of 5 years are thought to have oppositional defiant disorder (ODD), with boys outnumbering girls by two to one. Some of the typical behaviours of a child with ODD include:

- Easily angered, annoyed or irritated
- Frequent temper tantrums
- Argues frequently with adults, particularly the most familiar adults in their lives, such as parents
- Refuses to obey rules
- Seems to deliberately try to annoy or aggravate others
- Low self-esteem
- Low frustration threshold
- Seeks to blame others for any misfortunes or misdeeds.

From a sample of high risk children, groups of acting out, withdrawn, and normal preschool children were identified and followed through first, second, and third grade. A high degree of stability of developmental adaptation was found for each group. Examination of the exceptions to predicted outcomes indicated that discontinuity of development was accounted for by level and change in maternal depressive symptomatology, life circumstances, stressful life events experienced by the family, and quality of the home environment. Level of maternal depression appeared to directly affect the quality of care she provided her child, and indirectly affected the quality and organization of the home environment.

Need of the study

Schools play a crucial and formative role in the spheres of cognitive, language, emotional, social and moral development of children. There is now a growing recognition that schools have a significant role in promoting mental health. Teachers are powerful groups who have in their process of education studied the nature of individual growth. This has equipped them to be in a position to shape and reshape behaviours that are warranted.

Nearly one in five children and adolescents will have emotional and behavioural disorders at some time in their youth. Mental disorders in schools amount to 3.12% in students. Even by conservative estimates 10% of the child population suffers from mental disturbances with serious associated impairments including

learning problems, health problems and drug abuse at any given time. At least 3% of school age children suffer from serious emotional disturbances at any given point of time. Early detection of psychiatric problems in children is of

paramount importance. A few studies carried out in India revealed the prevalence of psychiatric morbidity to be 8-30% in children under 12 years of age. Thus, at any point in a given time, one out of five children in the general population has a clinically significant disorder.

Statement of Problem A study to assess the effectiveness of structured teaching programme on programme on knowledge regarding selected behavioural problems of pre-school children's parents at selected pre-school at Dewas M.P.

Objectives of the study

- To assess pre test knowledge score of mothers regarding selected behavioural problems of pre-school children's parents at selected pre-school at Dewas M.P
- To assess post test knowledge score of mothers regarding selected behavioural problems of pre-school children's parents at selected pre-school at Dewas M.P
- To find out the association between knowledge score with selected demographic variables.
- To assess effectiveness of planned teaching programme regarding selected behavioural problems of preschool children

1.1 Hypothesis

H1: There will be a significant difference between pre-test and post-test knowledge score regarding selected behavioural problems of pre-school children's parents at selected pre-school at Dewas M.P. at 0.05 level of significance.

H2: There will be a significant association between Pre-test knowledge score with their selected demographic variables at 0.05 level of significance.

Operational Definition

- ❖ **Assess:** According to “Oxford English dictionary” assess means to decide the amount or value of estimates the worth or likelihood of.
- ❖ In this study: It is a statistical measurement of knowledge score by using structured knowledge questioner.
- ❖ **Effectiveness:** A measure of the extent to which a specific intervention, procedure, regimen, or service, when deployed in the field in routine circumstances, does what it is intended to do for a specified population.
- ❖ In this study: Effect after implementation of planned teaching programme regarding selected behavioural problems of preschool children
- ❖ **Behavioural Problems:**
 - ❖ Refers to an abnormality of emotions, behaviour or relationship which insufficiently severe and persistent to handicap the child in his social or personal functioning and to cause distress to the child, their care givers and to the people in the community.
- ❖ **Children:**
 - ❖ Children refers to Pre school age children those who are upto age 3 Years
- ❖ **Structured teaching programme:**
 - ❖ It is the systematically developed teaching programme. In this study, it refers to the systematically planned teaching programme used in the study to improve the knowledge of mothers regarding selected behavioural problems.
- ❖ **Selected behavioural problems**
 - ❖ It refers to abnormal behaviour of children under age 3 years like Anxiety, Agree,

Depression, Attention seeking, Temper tantrum

❖ **Delimitation**

- ❖ The study is delimited to only a group mothers knowing to speak English & Hindi in pre-school children’s parents at selected pre-school at Dewas M.P.
- ❖ Mothers those are present at the time of data collection.

Ethical & Legal Consideration

- ❖ Written permission from the administrative authority of School
- ❖ Taking informed consent from mother
- ❖ Approving the study from ethical committee
- ❖ Not to cause any harm to any of the study participants.

5.1 Major finding

Section I

Findings regarding demographic variables

- The data show that majority 28.3 Percentage of mothers were in the age group of 24-28 years , 25% of mothers were in the age group of 21-23 years, and 25% mothers were in the age group of 29-33 years. There was a trace no. of mothers in age group of 33 and above years. Over all Majorities of the mothers were in the age group of 24-28 years
- The Educational status of mothers was, 6.6 Percentage were illiterate, 36.7% were in primary level, 21.7% were up to high school and 35.0% were up to higher secondary. Over all Most of the mothers (36.7%) had educational status up to primary level while only 6.6% of them were illiterate.
- The 50 percentage of mothers were labor, 21.7% mothers in private job and 21.7% in private job, and 21.7% mothers were in self

business and only 6.6% eligible couple in govt. job.

- **Section II**

Comparison of increase in knowledge of mothers with the pre testknowledge

- This study shows that there is a significant increase in knowledge of mothersafter the planned teaching programme Where the t-value is 18.525.
- Association between demographic variable and knowledge score on selected behavioural problems
- There was a significant $\chi^2 = 13.65$ (**P< 0.05**) association between age in years(grouped) and Pre-test score.
- There was a significant $\chi^2 = 18.01$ (**P< 0.05**) association between educationand pre-test score.
- There was a significant $\chi^2 = 21.92$ (**P< 0.05**) association between Occupationand pre-test score.
- There was a significant $\chi^2 = 24.61$ (**P< 0.05**) association between type offamily and pre-test score.

5.2 SUMMARY

The findings of the study shows that education will help to improve theknowledge of mothers regarding selected behavioural problems in preschool and this can in turn prevent further problems in the future. And help to have good growth & development of a children's

5.5 Conclusion

After the detailed analysis, this study leads to the following conclusion:

Data presented in table 7 shows that 36.7% mothers has poor knowledge regarding selected behavioural problems in pre school children's while 58.3% were found average in knowledge.

After the implementation of planned teaching programme there is a significant increase in knowledge of mothers regarding selected behavioural problems in pre school children's which is calculated by t-test and the result was - 18.52 (Table 10)

There was significant association between pre test knowledge on selected behavioural problems in pre school children's with selected demographic variable.

- The 50 percentage of mothers were labor, 21.7% mothers in private job and 21.7% in private job, and 21.7% mothers were in self business and only 6.6% eligible couple in govt. job.

- **Section II**

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- There was a significant $\chi^2 = 24.61$ ($P < 0.05$) association between type of family and pre-test score.

Methods:

Research design

The design is the structure of any scientific work. It gives direction and systematizes the research. Research design is the researcher's overall plan for obtaining answers to the research questions or for testing the research hypothesis. It is the overall plan for addressing a research question including specialization for enhancing the integrity of the study. Pre- test Post- test Research design was selected for the study.

Sampling technique

Sampling is a process of selecting a group of people, events or portion of the population to represent the entire population. Non probability convenient sampling technique was found appropriate to select 60 school children's mothers from theselected schools for the study.

In Non probability convenient sampling technique the researcher chooses the sample based on who they think would be appropriate for the study. This is used primarily when there is a limited number of people that have expertise in the area being researched. It is a type of Non probability convenient sampling technique in which the researcher selects subjects on the basis of personal judgment about which ones will be most representative of a specific population.

Setting

Setting is the physical location and conditions in which data collection takes place. The study was conducted at selected schools of Dewas, MP. The samples were selected using Non probability convenient sampling technique.

Result: This chapter presents the discussion of findings based on the sample characteristics, knowledge of mothers, effectiveness of planned teaching programme association between pre-test knowledge scores. The overall experience was a satisfying.

Interpretation and Conclusion:

After the detailed analysis, this study leads to the following conclusion:

Data presented in table 7 shows that 36.7% mothers has poor knowledge regarding selected behavioural problems in pre school children's while 58.3% were found average in knowledge.

After the implementation of planned teaching programme there is a significant increase in knowledge of mothers regarding selected behavioural problems in pre school children's which is calculated by t-test .

There was significant association between pre test knowledge on selected behavioural problems in pre school children's with selected demographic variable.

SUMMARY

This chapter explained the methodology for this study. It includes research approach, research design, variable under study, setting of the study, population, sample size and sampling, Sampling selecting criteria, data collection tools and

techniques, development of the tool, Preparation of blue print, description of the tool, content validity of tool, reliability of the tool, pilot study, procedure for data collection, plan for data analysis.

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How To Cite This:

APA STYLE: DR. MOHAMMED MOHSIN KHAN. (2023). "A Study To Assess The Effectiveness Of Structured Teaching Programme On Programme On Knowledge Regarding Selected Behavioural Problems Of Pre-School Children's Parents At Selected Pre-School At Dewas M.P.". In Brio International Journal of Nursing Research (BIJNR) (Vol. 4, Number 1, p. 95). BIJNR.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14620157>

VANCOUVER STYLE: DR. MOHAMMED MOHSIN KHAN. "A Study To Assess The Effectiveness Of Structured Teaching Programme On Programme On Knowledge Regarding Selected Behavioural Problems Of Pre-School Children's Parents At Selected Pre-School At Dewas M.P.". Vol. 4, Brio International Journal of Nursing Research (BIJNR). BIJNR; 2023 Jan p. 95.